

EDUCATION: STILL A DREAM FOR MARGINALIZED PEOPLE – A REFLECTION

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Abstract

Education is a weapon that obliterates ignorance and endeavours for the improvement of human and humanity as a whole. It acts as the key factor in bringing a positive societal change by instilling confidence and contravening the barriers that hamper the growth of people. The core purpose of the Indian Education system is to endow knowledge to the public without any prejudice and preconception, yet the marginalized people even today are ostracized from acquiring an education. While the Nation implements Education 4.0 and other modern technological advancements in the field of Education, the mere fact of getting educated is still a dream for the majority of the marginalized section of the society. They are barred from all facets of life, resulting in increasing violence and crimes against them. Studies underline the primary reason for their distress is their lack of education as most of the lower sections of the society are illiterates. Complimentary access to education remains ambiguous to them, as the provinces of Educational institutions do not welcome them. Even if they are permitted to learn, they are physically and psychologically tormented in the name of their social order resulting in dropping out from their studies. Thus, they remain suppressed and endure oppression for ages without a proper foundation. The status of these sections of women remains all the more pathetic as they are obstructed both by the upper strata and by men of their own groups. It is the need of the hour to delve into their lives as the world is witnessing an increasing number of brutal harassment against suppressed people across every domain of their livelihoods. This article aims at highlighting the reason of their deprivation, problems faced by them, elite class treatment in handling them, ways to restore equality and harmony in the mindset of people, and the solutions to provide the quality learning process in the education system.

Keywords: Education, Marginalized, Psychology, Society, Violence

Introduction

Regardless of seventy-two years of India's Independence from the British, the marginalized people even today remain as slaves in the hands of our very own land. Though the practice of Untouchability has been legally outlawed, it is predominantly widespread across the country. The Marginalized people, barred from all sects of the society and are treated to the lowest level even today. To define Marginalized people, it refers to a group of people who are socially excluded and does not enjoy the privileges like the rest of society. This division of people exclusively is vulnerable to exploitation. Besides, their sufferings go unnoticed and invisible as people perceive them to be sufferers in a religious context. According to the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, Marginalization is referred to as

“Different groups of people within a given culture, context and history at risk of being subjected to multiple discrimination due to the interplay of different personal characteristics or grounds, such as sex, gender, age, ethnicity, religion or belief, health status, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, education or income, or living in various geographic localities.”

The Oxford English Dictionary defines the term Marginalization as follows *“To render or treat as marginal; to remove from the centre or mainstream; to force (an individual, minority group, etc.) to the periphery of a dominant social group; (gen.) to belittle, depreciate, discount, or dismiss.”* In India, more than age, gender, disability and race, people are discriminated based on their social order. The major problem faced by India, is the stratification of people, according to the caste system. This classification provides benefits to the upper castes while the lower section of the society is destined to suffer. The upper strata of the society enjoyed all the privileges, while the marginalized group depends on the dominant class for survival, and this continues to date.

The people belonging to this group are neglected from all walks of the society, thereby hindering their growth in all spheres of their life likely socially, economically and politically. These people have little or no control over their lives and are deprived of sharing resources available. Their lives are the result of discrimination and the subordination they face from

dominant groups. They are vulnerable to all kinds of discriminations both physically, verbally and psychologically. They are openly assaulted in the name of their caste order publicly. They are refused entrance to temples, to fetch water from common wells, to live alongside the upper caste people, and not allowed to have a land of their own. On the other hand, they are denied education, and the majority of the people belong to this group remain illiterates. As they stay miserable, they find it difficult to have a meal for a day. These factors also lead to their poor hygiene, as they have no facilities for proper health care. To sum up, they are denied of all facets of life to sustain and remain poor throughout their life. In order to embrace their way of life, it is necessary to recognize the source of their predicament.

Causes of Illiteracy

According to the ancient religious text, it is believed the Varna system is the main cause of the stratification of people. Under this Varna system, four main categories are described which gradually turns to be the prevailing caste order. It is mentioned in Rig Veda, the ancient sacred text, the four categorization arises from the body parts of Lord Bhrama (Universal soul). Accordingly, the first to be created is the Brahmins from the mouth, followed by them is the Kshatriyas from the arms, the third order is the Vaishyas born from the thighs, and the last to be created is the Shudras originated from the feet.

The text prescribes duties to each category as follows: the Brahmins belong to the priestly class, the Kshatriyas belong to the warrior class, the Vaishyas belongs to the wealthy merchant and the peasant class, and the Shudras to perform servitude to the above three Varnas. As they are born from the feet, they are alleged to be servants in helping society. They were made to lead their families by the compensation they received from their services rendered to the above three groups. They are made to believe that it is because of their past actions and karma they were born in this category. Also, they were told through the words of the book, that if they perform their duties without questioning them, they will become eligible to be born in a higher caste in their next birth. This gives ample proof of how this sect of people was suppressed by the upper stratum.

Education is supposed to be the central strategy for bringing about the alterations necessary to ensure development both personally and to society. It is the weapon in bringing

about social changes, and to fight against injustice that hinders the growth of an individual. The root cause of illiteracy can be discovered in ancient times where the Shudras were forbidden from getting an education. This can be seen in the following verses of religious text as follows *“If a Sūdra intentionally overhears the Veda chants, he shall have his ears filled with molten tin and dark-red pigment. If a Sūdra dares to recite the chants himself, he will have his tongue cut out; and if he learns the chants by heart, his body shall be split in twain.”* The Shudras were completely uneducated while the other Varnas possesses some varying degrees of knowledge. These laws kept the Shudras in complete ignorance by placing them outside the mainstream of society.

This paves ways to the corrosion of education to the Shudras and their successors. This imposing of strict punishments barred them from all privileges of their life. It marks the beginning of making people unaware of their rights by denying them access to knowledge by making them illiterates and thus marginalizing them in all spheres of life. The worst part is that it continues to date even after the World witness modern advancements enhanced in the education system. As Jyotirao Phule, an Indian social reformer, once said: *“For want of education, intellect deteriorated; for want of intellect, morality decayed; for want of morality, progress stopped; for want of progress, wealth vanished; for want of wealth, Shudras perished.”*

This persistent illiteracy has perpetuated a cycle of poverty, where marginalized groups are unable to improve their social standing or participate fully in society. The lack of access to education keeps them trapped in menial jobs, often without the skills necessary to secure better opportunities, thus reinforcing their marginalized status.

Challenges Faced by Marginalized Women

Marginalized women in India face a unique and compounded set of challenges due to both caste and gender-based discrimination. These women are subjected to the oppressive caste system, which relegates them to the lowest social strata, and patriarchal norms that limit their roles to domestic duties. According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), in 2020, there were 31,677 cases of sexual assault (of which a significant portion involved marginalized women), and a significant number of these cases involved Dalit women. Studies indicate that

Dalit women are disproportionately impacted by sexual violence in rural areas. In addition, early marriage and sexual violence are prevalent, causing many girls to drop out or never attend school at all. India has the highest number of child brides in the world. According to UNICEF, approximately 27% of girls in India are married before the age of 18, and this percentage is notably higher in marginalized communities. For example, in Scheduled Tribe areas, child marriage rates can reach up to 40%. Women from marginalized communities face significant economic deprivation. A report by the National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) found that 80% of Dalit women work in the informal economy, often in low-paid and hazardous jobs, making education unaffordable. As a result, access to education becomes a distant dream for many.

Moreover, caste-based bullying and gender bias in schools contribute to psychological trauma, such as low self-esteem, stress, and depression, which further discourage them from pursuing education. Despite legal protections and policies aimed at improving their situation, societal attitudes and lack of enforcement continue to perpetuate their marginalization.

Hardships and Austerities Faced

It is legal and globally proclaimed that every child in the world has the right to access quality education without any discrimination and exclusion. Although after implementing several acts and policies for the betterment of marginalized people and their welfare, the condition of these people remains miserable. Special acts, particularly Article 46 of the Constitution of India, promote the educational interests exclusively for the betterment of the marginalized groups and fight to protect them from all forms of exploitation. However, these people even today suffer from achieving their dreams.

These children are denied even at the ingress of the Educational Institution upon knowing their background. Various studies have come out with a shocking report saying that all most majority of the illiterates are marginalized people who hardly passed their primary education. Added to it most of the children in this group are found to be workers in various fields. As they remain in poverty, they consider working in order to support their family rather focusing on their academics. Even if some children are blessed to receive an education, they are made to drop out

from their studies half away due to other bullying and maltreating them in the name of their social order.

For instance, the suicidal history of Rohit Vemula, a Dalit student at the University of Hyderabad, tragically took his own life in 2016 after facing caste-based discrimination and institutional bias. His death highlighted the systemic exclusion and marginalization of Dalit students in India's higher education system. Despite his academic excellence, Vemula was suspended after being involved in a protest, which many saw as an act of caste-based victimization. His suicide sparked nationwide protests, drawing attention to the pervasive caste discrimination in universities and the challenges Dalit students face, including mental health struggles and social exclusion. Vemula's case underscored the need for greater reforms in India's educational institutions to ensure equality and inclusivity for marginalized communities. The victims are often the people of the marginalized group who ended their life without even obtaining a degree of the course they registered. These gruesome incidents portray how these people are tormented, humiliated, isolated and bullied in the name of the social order. Prejudice and discrimination continue to survive till date endangering the lives of the secluded people.

The Psychological Impact of Discrimination

The effects of caste-based discrimination go beyond physical harm. Psychological trauma, such as low self-esteem, stress, anxiety, and depression, often accompanies the exclusion experienced by marginalized communities. The constant reminder of their "inferior" status, whether through caste-based slurs or institutional bias, can leave lasting emotional scars, further hindering their ability to succeed in education or in life.

The Way Forward: Bridging the Gap

Education is the most powerful tool to break the cycle of marginalization. To create a truly inclusive society, the education system must be restructured to eliminate caste-based discrimination and provide equal opportunities for all. This can be achieved by:

1. **Curriculum Reforms:** Introducing curriculum changes that address issues of caste-based discrimination and promote social justice and equality.

2. **Improving Access:** Expanding access to quality education for marginalized communities, particularly through scholarships, free textbooks, and providing a safe environment in schools.
3. **Community Support:** Encouraging community-based initiatives that support the education of marginalized children and help bridge the cultural and social divides.
4. **Stronger Enforcement of Laws:** Strengthening the enforcement of laws that protect the educational rights of marginalized communities and ensuring accountability for those who perpetrate caste-based discrimination.

Conclusion

It is no doubt that education is mandatory to equip oneself to actively participate in social life and to enrich one's own capability and talents to sustain in the world. Education is a potent tool to make a person deserving and fit to advance their opinions against all odds of their life. The crucial need to be implemented in teaching is to include curriculum that eradicates the differences and social injustice, and to promote justness and equality without any bias. The Government should also play a vital role in checking the dropout rate of marginalized people from educational institutions and should investigate the problems endured by them. This can be achieved by strengthening the legal rules against such crimes and adopting committees to look after the issue. Apart from this, every citizen of the country should take responsibility for building a society without any discrimination. People should be cooperative, mutually respect others feelings and opinions, treat every being with dignity and should ensure a safe environment for fellow human beings.

References

- Spivak G (1986) Feminism and critical theory. In: *In Other Worlds: Essays in Cultural Politics*. Methuen: London, pp 77–92.
- Oliver K (2009) *Animal Lessons: How They Teach Us To Be Human*. Columbia University Press: New York.
- Maggio J (2007) Can the subaltern be heard: Political theory, translation, representation, and Gayatri Chakravorty Sivak. *Alternatives*; **32** (4): 419–443.
- Kristeva J (1981) Women's Time. *Signs*; **7** (1): 13–35.

Eisenstein Z (2004) *Against Empire: Feminisms, Racism, and The West*. Zed Books: London.

Jones, N. (2004) “‘It’s Not Where You Live, It’s How You Live’: How Young Women Negotiate Conflict and Violence in the Inner City’, *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 595: 49-62 .

Tiwari, M., & Pandey, S. (2021). *Educational Inclusion of Marginalized Groups in India: Challenges and Opportunities*. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(2), 102-110.

Booth, T., & Ainscow, M. (2011). *The index for inclusion: Developing learning and participation in schools* (3rd ed.). Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education (CSIE).

Sen, A. (1999). *Development as Freedom*. Oxford University Press.

Manusmriti. Translated by Wendy Doniger, *The Laws of Manu*, Penguin Classics, 1991.

National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO). (2018). *Key Indicators of Household Social Consumption in India: Education* (Report No. 587). Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India.

Sarkar, S., & Gupta, R. (2019). The role of education in empowering marginalized women in rural India. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 64(3), 45-58.

European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA). (2019). *Fundamental rights report 2019*. European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights.